

Questionnaire for Word Domains

402 Warembor

Compiler: Alena Witzlack-Makarevich 2003-10-03

Source: Mark Donohue, *Warembori Grammar Sketch*

Note: As the book is just a sketch most of the questions remained unanswered.

I. Segmental Properties

Describe phonotactic patterns and restrictions on both lexemes and grammatical morphemes. Describe the locations of these phenomena (e.g. syllable-final, initial...). If identifiable loanwords or other words are excluded, note this.

Describe phonological processes where reference is made to domains (special attention should be given to gemination, epenthesis, lengthening, vowel or cons. harmony)

Word-internal:

lenition of voiced stops: any occurrences of intervocalic /b/ or /d/ appear as a lenited [B] or [r], respectively; thus, we find alternations such as

/dodo-/ + /dan-/ → [dororan.do]
'rain' 'water' '(It is) rainwater'

cf. across word boundaries:

*/nana/ + /dan-do/ → [nanadando], * [nanarando]*
'in' 'water-IND' 'in the water'

nasal assimilation: nasal + stop clusters are homo-organic;

/waren-/ + /bo-/ → [warEmbo.ro]
'river' 'mouth' '(It is a) mouth of a river'

/waren-/ + /-do/ → [warEn.do]
'river' 'IND' '(It is a) river.'

What is the default syllable template for both lexemes and grammatical forms?

The language basically allows syllables of the shape CV(N), with the only final coda allowed being the nasal (which assimilates in place to a following consonant), the r, and the y.

Is there an explicitly stated minimal word requirements? (This may be stated in terms of obligatory vowel length or syllable structure in monosyllabic words)

'Most roots are of at least two syllables length, though a small minority are found with only one syllable; in these cases, the presence of the indicative is compulsory, making them then two (or more) syllables long in pronunciation.' > minimally two syllables

II. Prosodic Properties

If stress is not explicitly discussed but is marked, where is primary stress located (initial, pre-final, final...), and is it a fixed system?

Stress is normally assigned to the penultimate syllable of a word or compound. This penultimate position shifts with affixation, so that, for instances, we have

<i>/mena/</i>	<i>/mena-do/</i>	<i>/mena-na-o/</i>
<i>dog</i>	<i>dog-IND</i>	<i>dog-PL-IND</i>
<i>[ˈmEna]</i>	<i>[mEˈnaro]</i>	<i>[mEnaˈnao]</i>

Exceptions to this are found if a) the root ends in a nasal, or b) all the vowels in the word are the same (not specified); (the presence of one of the heavy consonants in a word might also affect stress)

a) In the event that the root ends in a nasal, and there are two non-contiguous vowels, we find that stress does not shift with the addition of suffixes. compare the treatment of mena 'dog' above with waren 'river':

<i>/waren/</i>	<i>/waren-do/</i>	<i>/waren-na-o/</i>
<i>river</i>	<i>river-IND</i>	<i>river-PL-IND</i>
<i>[ˈwaEn]</i>	<i>[ˈwarEndo]</i>	<i>[ˈwarEnao]</i>

c) a syllable beginning with a heavy consonant always bears the stress. Compare the stress patterns in the following minimal pair:

<i>/bo-do/</i>	<i>/'bo-do/</i>	<i>(ˈb= heavy consonant)</i>
<i>fruit-IND</i>	<i>thorn-IND</i>	
<i>[boˈro]</i>	<i>[ˈboro]</i>	

What are the rhythmic patterns and what is the direction (e.g. trochee, iamb, unbounded)? To what constituents is stress attracted (V:, VV, VC, etc.)? Is it quantity sensitive?

Does stress serve any morpho-syntactic function? If so, explain.

Do stress demarcations highlight or illustrate morpheme boundaries across a morphologically complex word? Do different morphemes have different stress patterns?

Describe stress patterns with regard to compounding. Do prosodic rules apply across compounds, or are they restricted to internal position?

p. 14: In compounds, the primary stress stays with the first component of the compound, and does not shift; the second component of the compound does not receive a stress. In terms of stress assignment, then, the compounds of Warembori do not behave as single phonological words for stress assignment, but neither do they behave as two totally independent words.

III. Morpho-Syntax

Discuss the degree and types of fusion between morpheme boundaries. If there are differences between morphemes, please note this. Describe any non-adjacent allomorphy, or allomorphy that violates adjacency conditions or that goes across words. Refer to Bickel and Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/~bickel/research/papers/index.html>) for relevant terminology & definitions

Is there any infixation, circumfixation or simulfixation? What are the patterns? What reduplication patterns are described? What is copied (total vs. partial)? If reduplication is partial, is it described in terms of segmental sequences or prosodic units (e.g. the foot with specific restrictions, or in terms of a template)? In reduplication is there any segment mutation (e.g. devoicing, vowel place-of-articulation change)? Does the resulting reduplicated form defy the default phonotactic or prosodic properties of the language?

Describe the relevant distribution and phonological properties of clitics and particles.

IV. Other Questions

Do unstressed vowels undergo any kind of reduction? What happens to unbounded feet?

Describe word-word combinations (e.g. compounds, incorporation, complex predicates).

There are two types of incorporation, only the second type is described in details, but I think that the statements from this description apply to the first type as well:

- a) noun incorporation by verbs (preverbal)*
- b) Postverbal incorporation can take referential nouns, even ones compounded with adjectives or suffixed with deictics, and incorporate them. The incorporation can be demonstrated by the appearance of object suffixes or applicatives following the incorporated nominal, and the phonological interaction with the verb root (stress, assimilation patterns described above).*

*E-mune-mena-ro. [E'munE,mEna,ro]
mE'naro]
ISG-kill-dog-IND
'I killed a dog.'*

*E-mune mena-ro. [E'munE
ISG-kill dog-IND*

Describe bipartite stems (read the relevant discussion in the inflectional morphology chapter).

Periphrastic morphology: state which forms are formed peripherally and what the general template is (e.g. Aux + Stem; Aux + inflected form; Aux + Particle; Aux + Converb).

Note all of the properties listed by the author describing pre and post-positions.

?? There appear to be three prepositional formatives, na, ka and ta, and one unanalysable preposition kombe. These may not, however, appear on their own, and in prepositional use must be either reduplicated or compounded together.

Of interest:

A difference must be made between alienable and inalienable possession, based not on the form of the pronominal marker, but on its phonological cohesion with the noun.

Compare the forms in the following minimally contrastive phrases:

<i>e=</i>	<i>bo-</i>	<i>ro</i>	<i>e-</i>	<i>voro-</i>	<i>ro</i>
<i>ISG=</i>	<i>coconut-</i>	<i>IND</i>	<i>ISG-</i>	<i>tongue-</i>	<i>IND</i>
	<i>'my coconut'</i>			<i>'my tongue'</i>	

In the first of these examples we can see that the initial consonant in coconut, /b/, is present in its [b] allophone, indicating that the preceding e is not part of the same phonological word as it is. In the b sentence, however, we see that the initial /b/ in 'tongue' appears with the [B] allophone, showing that the preceding e in this case is part of the same phonological word. Although the forms of the two affixes are the same for both alienable and inalienable use, their degrees of bondedness with the following nouns are different.